

13. Shi Y., Vanhoutte P. M. Macro- and microvascular endothelial dysfunction in diabetes. *J Diabetes*. 2017. Vol. 9, No. 5. P. 434-449.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1753-0407.12521>

14. Su J. B. Vascular endothelial dysfunction and pharmacological treatment. *World J Cardiol*. 2015. Vol. 7, No. 11. P. 719-741.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4330/wjc.v7.i11.719>

15. Yaribeygi H., Sathyapalan T., Atkin S. L., Sahebkar A. Molecular Mechanisms Linking Oxidative Stress and Diabetes Mellitus. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2020. 8609213.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8609213>

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ROLE OF GUT MICROBIOTA IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Ключові слова: *цукровий діабет 2 типу, кишкова мікробіота, метаболіти кишкової мікробіоти, інкретини, субклінічне запалення*

Ключевые слова: *сахарный диабет 2 типа, кишечная микробиота, метаболиты кишечной микробиоты, инкретини, субклиническое воспаление*

Abstract. Role of gut microbiota in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes mellitus (literature review). Koval S.M., Snihurska I.O. *Type 2 diabetes mellitus is an extremely common disease that leads to the development of life-threatening complications but its pathogenesis remains poorly understood. One of the promising directions in this area is the study of disorders of gut microbiota. Literature data indicate that a number of quantitative and qualitative changes in the composition of the gut microbiota are the most important factors in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Bacteria of the genera Ruminococcus, Fusobacterium and Blautia are most involved in the pathogenesis of this disease. The participation of the gut microbiota in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes mellitus is due to its*

metabolites, which play an important role in the regulation of the permeability and integrity of the intestinal wall, the expression of specific intestinal receptors, incretin secretion, gluconeogenesis activity, chronic subclinical inflammation, and even in adipose tissue remodeling. Further in-depth study of gut microbiota disorders is promising in order to develop fundamentally new approaches to the treatment and prevention of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Реферат. Роль кишечной микробиоты в патогенезе сахарного диабета 2 типа (обзор литературы).

Коваль С.Н., Снегурская И.А. Сахарный диабет 2 типа – чрезвычайно распространенное заболевание, которое приводит к развитию жизнеопасных осложнений, однако его патогенез остается не достаточно выясненным. Одним из перспективных направлений в этой области является изучение нарушений кишечной микробиоты. Данные литературы свидетельствуют о том, что целый ряд количественных и качественных изменений состава кишечной микробиоты является важнейшими факторами патогенеза сахарного диабета 2 типа. В наибольшей степени в патогенез данного заболевания вовлечены бактерии родов *Ruminococcus*, *Fusobacterium* и *Blautia*. Участие кишечной микробиоты в патогенезе сахарного диабета 2 типа обусловлено ее метаболитами, которые играют важную роль в регуляции проницаемости и целостности стенки кишечника, экспрессии специфических рецепторов кишечника, секреции инкретинов, активности глюконеогенеза, хронического субклинического воспаления и даже в ремоделировании жировой ткани. Перспективным является дальнейшее углубленное изучение нарушений кишечной микробиоты с целью разработки принципиально новых подходов к лечению и профилактике сахарного диабета 2 типа.

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) is a highly common multifactorial disease that leads to the development of life-threatening complications and premature death of patients [46]. Given the great medical and social importance of the problem of type 2 diabetes, intensive studies of the main mechanisms of its pathogenesis are carried out, including genetic predisposition to type 2 diabetes and candidate genes associated with this disease [1, 4], insulin resistance (IR) [1, 4], disorders of glucagon, incretins [4, 41], cytokines and adipokines [20, 26, 27, 37], various neurohumoral factors [4, 35, 41]. However, despite this, the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes remains unclear.

One of the promising areas of research on the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes is the study of the role of gut microbiota (GM) disorders.

The purpose of this work is to review the literature on the problem of studying the role of GM disorders in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes.

The search for literature was carried out in scientific databases Google Scholar, PubMed, Web of science, Scopus. Relevant scientific publications for the period 2014-2020 were selected to determine the state of GM in patients with type 2 diabetes and changes in GM at the stage of prediabetes. The search terms were: "gut microbiota", "sequencing", "type 2 diabetes", "pathogenesis".

GM, due to its multifaceted impact on the entire metabolic system of the body, is recognized as a full-fledged functional "organ" that plays an important role in digestion, nutrition, immune regulation and metabolism. It was found that more than 90% of GM of a healthy person is represented by *Bacteroidetes* and *Firmicutes*, including representatives of the genera *Lactobacillus*, *Clostridium* and *Ruminococcus*. *Actinobacteria*, *Verrucomicrobia* and *Fusobacteria* are also part of GM, but in much smaller quantities [3, 41].

To date, the role of GM in the development of a number of diseases and, above all, diseases of the gastrointestinal and urogenital tract, skin, nasopharynx, allergic, autoimmune and cancer diseases, as well as obesity, atherosclerosis, hypertension and many others received evidence [2, 3, 5, 41]. In recent years this list also includes type 2 diabetes [10, 11, 16].

Studies show that already at the stage of prediabetes the following changes in the composition of GM are observed in comparison with healthy individuals: decrease in the total content of bacteria of the *Clostridiales* series against the background of increasing content of such representatives as *Dorea*, *Ruminococcus*, *Sutterella* and *Streptococcus*; reduction in the number of bacteria that decompose mucin - *Akkermansia muciniphila*, belonging to the type *Verrucomicrobia* [6]. Most studies on changes of GM in patients with type 2 diabetes have reported an increase in bacteria of the genera *Ruminococcus*, *Fusobacterium*, and *Blautia*, and a decrease in the number of bacteria of the genera *Bifidobacterium*, *Bacteroides*, *Faecalibacterium*, *Akkermansia*, and *Roseburia* in the gut of these patients [11, 13, 33, 36]. However, there are conflicting data regarding the association of *Blautia* bacteria with type 2 diabetes. Thus, in the work of Tong X. et al. (2018) it is shown that the number of *Blautia* bacteria in patients with type 2 diabetes increases after a significant improvement in carbohydrate and lipid metabolism under the influence of antidiabetic therapy [42].

A number of studies has shown a positive correlation between *Bacteroidetes* / *Firmicutes* and *Bacteroides-Prevotella* / *Clostridium Coccoides-Eubacterium rectale* with plasma glucose levels [10]. At the same time, the analysis of data from 42 studies did not confirm the association of the ratio of *Bacteroidetes* / *Firmicutes* with type 2 diabetes [36].

Of interest are studies of the association of bacteria of the genus *Lactobacillus* with impaired carbohydrate homeostasis and type 2 diabetes. These bacteria are gram-positive rod-shaped ones, facultative anaerobes are the main part of the group of lactic acid bacteria that convert sugar into lactic acid. An increase in the number of these bacteria in the gut of patients with prediabetes and type 2 diabetes compared to healthy individuals has been shown [36]. However, the results of the research are not homogeneous. Thus, in patients with type 2 diabetes there is, on the one hand, an increase in the number of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus gasseri*, *Lactobacillus Salivarius*, and on the other – a decrease in the number of *Lactobacillus amylovorus* [36]. There are also conflicting data on the testing of some species of *Lactobacillus* as probiotics and their effect on carbohydrate metabolism. Thus, *Lactobacillus sporogenes*, *Lactobacillus casei* Shirota and *Lactobacillus reuteri* improve carbohydrate metabolism in patients with type 2 diabetes [18, 19, 21, 41], but in most cases in combination with bacteria of the genus *Bifidobacterium* [36]. In addition to studies examining changes in the quantitative composition of various bacteria, information on the main mechanisms by which GM affects carbohydrate metabolism is important for understanding the role of GM disorders in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes.

Bacterial production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFA), which are produced in the human colon and cecum after anaerobic fermentation of indigestible dietary fiber with the help of sugar bacteria can be one of the significant mechanisms of this effect of GM. Their main representatives – acetate, propionate and butyrate make up 95% of SCFA and are one of the most common compounds obtained with the participation of GM. Studies show that the deficiency of SCFA synthesis is associated with the development of type 2 diabetes [16, 36]. However, there is evidence that butyrate induces the expression of genes involved in intestinal gluconeogenesis, and propionate itself is a substrate of gluconeogenesis [16]. Zhao L. et al. (2018) showed that not all, but only a small number of microbial strains are involved in the production of SCFA [17].

An important feature of SCFA is the ability to affect the permeability of the intestinal wall. It has been suggested that increased intestinal permeability may lead to damage to pancreatic β -cells due to increased absorption of exogenous antigens. Experimental studies prove the ability of butyrate to improve the integrity of the intestinal wall [16]. Thus, Xu Y.H. et al. (2018) showed that oral administration of butyrate significantly reduced the levels of HbA1c, inflammatory cytokines and

lipopolysaccharides in plasma in db/db mice, and after treatment with butyrate, local infiltration of inflammatory cells decreased, intestinal integrity increased and intercellular adhesion elevated [40].

The discovery of their receptors was important for understanding the role of SCFA, which allowed us to consider SCFA as important signaling molecules. Two GLC-activated G protein-coupled receptors have been described and identified as modulators of host-microbiota interaction: GPR41 and GPR43. These receptors are also known as free fatty acid receptors: FFAR3 and FFAR2, respectively. They have been found in the gut, sympathetic nervous system, liver, white adipose tissue, skeletal muscle, pancreas and immune tissues [16, 25, 41].

Experimental studies have shown that SCFA, mainly through GPR43 receptors (FFAR2), are able to stimulate the secretion of a number of intestinal peptide hormones, including incretin-glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) [16, 44].

Incretins play an important role in the regulation of insulin secretion and appetite. Incretins, in addition to GLP-1, include gastric inhibitory polypeptide (GIP). These hormones, released from enteroendocrine cells, are secreted into the bloodstream and rapidly stimulate insulin secretion from β -cells in response to food intake [4].

Faerch K. et al. (2015) in a clinical study of 1462 people showed a decrease in GLP-1 secretion in response to oral glucose loading in patients with type 2 diabetes, as well as in patients with prediabetes and obesity, compared with normal body mass and normal glucose tolerance, which indicates a disorder of GLP-1 secretion at the stage of prediabetes [14].

It has also been shown that type 2 diabetes mellitus develops specific dysbiosis that induces resistance to GLP-1 [9].

One of the ways in which GM affects the secretion of incretins is the increase in the number of enteroendocrine L-cells in the gut. Experimental studies have shown that the number of enteroendocrine L-cells doubled in the proximal colon of rats treated with oligofructose, which contributed to higher production of endogenous GLP-1 [10]. It has also been shown that the addition of indigestible carbohydrates, such as oligofructose, improves glucose tolerance, reduces IP and food consumption, which has been associated with increased plasma GLP-1 levels [16].

There is also evidence that some GM bacteria may affect the secretion of incretins through the products of their own metabolism. Thus, it was found that sulfate-reducing bacteria produce

hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) in the colon, which can directly stimulate the secretion of GLP-1 [33]. At the same time, there is evidence of an inhibitory effect of H₂S on the release of GLP-1 in vitro [35], which indicates the need for further research to clarify the role of sulfate-reducing bacteria in complex glucose metabolism.

As shown by experimental studies, another metabolite of GM – indole, formed during the dissimilation of tryptophan in GM, is able to regulate the secretion of GLP-1 from enteroendocrine L-cells of the mouse colon: to increase – in case of short-term exposure, but reduce – in the long term, i.e. to play the role of a signaling molecule through which GM can interact with enteroendocrine cells and change the glycemic control of the host [16].

One of the mechanisms of GM's effect on incretin secretion is mediated by its effect on the intestinal nervous system – on nerve cells of the myenteric plexus, which leads to decreased expression of GLP-1 receptor and stimulation of gastrointestinal motility [24].

Thus, the regulation of incretin production by modulating the parameters of GM can open a new direction in the treatment of type 2 diabetes [9]. In this regard, the possibility of direct effects on insulin secretion and β -cell proliferation through FFA2 and FFA3 receptors is very promising [15, 38].

Analyzing the possible ways of GM influence on glucose metabolism in the human body, it is also necessary to dwell on the bacterial metabolism of bile acids (BA). It is known that primary BA (choleic and chenodeoxycholic) are formed in the liver from cholesterol, and secondary BA (deoxycholic, lithocholic, alocholic and ursodeoxycholic) are formed in the colon from primary ones under the influence of GM. Thus, *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* produce bile salt hydrolases, which convert primary conjugated bile salts into deconjugated (primary) BA, which are subsequently converted into secondary ones [10].

BA regulate their own hepatic synthesis through a negative feedback mechanism, which involves a direct interaction between the BA and the farnesoid X-receptor (FXR – farnesoid X receptor) in hepatocytes and enterocytes of the ileum. The expression of fibroblast growth factor-19 (FGF-19) is induced in the ileum, which enters the circulation and further inhibits the synthesis of BA [10, 16]. FXR is expressed in a variety of metabolically active tissues, including the liver, intestines, and white adipose tissue. Conjugated and unconjugated BA can interact with FXR, with chenodeoxycholic acid being their strongest activator, while other BA are likely to be FXR antagonists [10, 16].

BA are potent signaling molecules, mainly due to their interaction with the FXR receptor and the membrane-G protein-coupled receptor TGR5 [10]. It has been shown that BA, by activating FXR and TGR5, are involved in the regulation of glucose homeostasis and energy metabolism - activation of intestinal FXR can both reduce and increase IR in obesity [22, 23, 39]. In addition to FXR and TGR5, FGF19, which stimulates glycogen synthesis in the liver in the postprandial state, may be an important regulator of blood glucose levels [10, 16].

The effect of GM on glucose metabolism can also be carried out through the regulation of inflammatory processes, in particular in adipose tissue [12, 45]. The association of chronic inflammation of adipose tissue in obesity, IR and type 2 diabetes has now been proven [16]. There is a strong and unique metabolic interaction between the intestine and peripheral white adipose tissue through compounds and metabolites produced or induced by GM, which affect the state of carbohydrate metabolism of the host [45]. An association between intestinal bacteria and inflammation has been identified through the identification of intestinal bacterial lipopolysaccharide, an inflammatory factor that plays an important role in the development of IR, obesity and type 2 diabetes [10]. A number of studies have shown that some representatives of GM are able to inhibit the production of large amounts of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines. Thus, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus paracasei*, *Lactobacillus casei* can reduce the level of interleukin (IL)-1 β , protein-1 chemoattractant monocytes, intercellular adhesion molecules-1, IL-8 and C-reactive protein [8, 29]; *Lactobacillus paracasei* and *Bifidobacterium fragilis* inhibit the expression of IL-6 [28, 36]; *Lactobacillus*, *Bacteroides* and *Akkermansia* inhibit the production of tumor necrosis factor- α [7, 28, 36]; *Lactobacillus paracasei*, *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and bacteria that produce butyrate – *Roseburia intestinalis* and *Faecalibacterium*, inhibit the activity of nuclear factor NF- κ B [28, 30, 36]; *Lactobacillus casei* and *Roseburia intestinalis* reduce the production of the proinflammatory cytokine interferon (IFN)- γ [17] and, in addition, *Roseburia intestinalis* inhibits the synthesis of IL-17 [37].

There are also papers indicating the induction of anti-inflammatory IL-10 synthesis by such bacterial species as *Roseburia intestinalis*, *Bacteroides fragilis*, *Akkermansia muciniphila*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus casei*, which is associated with improved glucose metabolism [36]. Increased expression of this cytokine in the muscles of mice

has been shown to prevent the development of aging-related IR [20].

Of great interest are the data that the components of GM can regulate the energy metabolism of the host by remodeling adipose tissue. Thus, Kim M. et al. (2017) in an experimental study showed that KetoA [10-oxo-12 (Z) -octadecenoic acid], a metabolite of linoleic acid produced by intestinal lactic acid bacteria, activates genes involved in the functioning of brown adipocytes, including transmembrane protein thermogenin-1 in white adipose tissue. This further increases energy expenditure in mice and thus reduces metabolic disorders associated with obesity [43].

Another experimental study [31] showed an increase in the amount of brown adipose tissue under the action of GM products, which increased tissue sensitivity to insulin, as well as reducing the size of white fat and adipocytes in lean mice and in various models of mice obesity. A significant contribution to the above processes is made by the LCDs described above, probably through the TGR5 receptor [16].

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the data accumulated in the literature suggest that a number of quantitative and qualitative changes in the composition of the intestinal microbiota are the most important factors in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes. Bacteria of the genera *Ruminococcus*, *Fusobacterium* and *Blautia* are most involved in the pathogenesis of this disease. The participation of intestinal microbiota in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes is primarily due to its metabolites, which play an important role in regulating the permeability and integrity of the intestinal wall, expression of specific intestinal receptors, secretion of incretins, gluconeogenesis, chronic subclinical inflammation and chronic subclinical inflammation. adipose tissue remodeling. Further in-depth study of GM disorders is promising in order to develop fundamentally new approaches to the treatment and prevention of type 2 diabetes.

Conflict of interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Belousova ON, Sirotina SS, Yakunchenko TI, Zhernakova NI. [Molecular and genetic mechanisms of the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes mellitus]. *Nauchnye vedomosti BelGU. Ser. Meditsina. Farmatsiya*. 2015;16(213):12-19. Russian. Available from: <https://dspace.bsu.edu.ru/handle/123456789/23761>
2. Koval SM, Yushko KO, Snihurska IO. [Gut microbiota and hypertension (a literature review)]. *Zaporozhskii meditsinskii zhurnal*. 2020.22(4):561-67. Ukrainian. doi: <https://doi.org/10.14739/2310-1210.2020.4.208409>
3. Lyzogub VG, Kramarova VN, Melnychuk IO. [Role of intestinal microbiota changes in cardiovascular diseases pathogenesis (a literature review)]. *Zaporozhskii meditsinskii zhurnal*. 2019.21(116):672-678. Ukrainian. doi: <https://doi.org/10.14739/2310-1210.2019.5.179462>
4. [Type 2 diabetes mellitus: from theory to practice], editors I.I. Dedova, M.V. Shestakova. Moskva: OOO "Izdatelstvo "Meditsinskoe informatsionnoe agentstvo"; 2016. p. 576. Russian.
5. Fadeenko GD, Gridnev AE. [Irritable bowel syndrome and gut microbiome. From pathogenetic mechanisms to treatment]. *Gastroenterologiya*. 2018.52(4):24-29. Russian.
6. Allin KH, Tremaroli V, Caesar R, Jensen BAH, Damgaard MTF, Bahl MI, et al. Aberrant intestinal microbiota in individuals with prediabetes. *Diabetologia*. 2018;61:810-20. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-018-4550-1>
7. Zhang L, Qin Q, Liu M, Zhang X, He F, Guoqing Wang G, et al. *Akkermansia muciniphila* can reduce the damage of gluco/lipotoxicity, oxidative stress and inflammation, and normalize intestine microbiota in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Pathog and Dis*. 2018;76(4). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/femspd/fty028>
8. Tian P, Li B, He C, Song W, Hou A, Tian S, et al. Antidiabetic (type 2) effects of lactobacillus G15 and Q14 in rats through regulation of intestinal permeability and microbiota. *Food Funct*. 2016;7:3789-97. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6fo00831c>
9. Grasset E, Puel A, Charpentier J, Collet X, Christensen JE, Terci F, et al. A specific gut microbiota dysbiosis of type 2 diabetic mice induces GLP-1 resistance through an enteric NO-dependent and gut-brain axis mechanism. *Cell Metab*. 2017;26:278. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2017.06.003>
10. Aw W, Fukuda S. Understanding the role of the gut ecosystem in diabetes mellitus. *J Diabetes Investig*. 2018;9:5-12. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdi.12673>
11. Aydin W, Nieuwdorp M, Gerdes V. The gut microbiome as a target for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. *Curr Diab Rep*. 2018;18(8):55. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-018-1020-6>
12. Bleau C, Karelis AD, St-Pierre DH, Lamontagne L. Crosstalk between intestinal microbiota, adipose tissue and skeletal muscle as an early event in systemic low-grade inflammation and the development of obesity and diabetes. *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2015;31:545-61. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/dmrr.2617>
13. Murphy R, Rinki Murphy, Tsai P, Jmllig M, Liu A, Plank L, Booth M. Differential changes in gut microbiota after gastric bypass and sleeve gastrectomy

- bariatric surgery vary according to diabetes remission. *Obes Surg.* 2017;27:917-25.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11695-016-2399-2>
14. Faerch K, Torekov SS, Vistisen D, Johansen NB, Witte DR, Jonsson A, et al. GLP-1 response to oral glucose is reduced in prediabetes, screen-detected type 2 diabetes, and obesity and influenced by sex: the ADDITION-PRO study. *Diabetes.* 2015;64:2513-25.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.2337/db14-1751>
15. McNelis JC, Lee YS, Mayoral R, van der Kant R, Johnson AM, Wollam J, et al. GPR43 potentiates beta-cell function in obesity. *Diabetes.* 2015;64:3203-17.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.2337/db14-1938>
16. Grard C, Vidal H. Impact of Gut Microbiota on Host Glycemic Control. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).* 2019;30:10-29.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2019.00029>
17. Zhao L, Zhang F, Ding X, Wu G, Lam YY, Wang X, et al. Gut bacteria selectively promoted by dietary fibers alleviate type 2 diabetes. *Science.* 2018;359:1151-6.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao5774>
18. Harsch IA, Konturek PC. The role of gut microbiota in obesity and type 2 and type 1 diabetes mellitus: new insights into “Old” diseases. *Med Sci.* 2018;6:E32.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/medsci6020032>
19. Hulston CJ, Churnside AA, Venables MC. Probiotic supplementation prevents high-fat, overfeeding-induced insulin resistance in human subjects. *Br J Nutr.* 2015;113(4):596-602.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114514004097>
20. Dagdeviren S, Jung DY, Friedline RH, Noh HL, Kim JH, Patel PR et al. IL-10 prevents aging-associated inflammation and insulin resistance in skeletal muscle. *FASEB J.* 2017 Feb;31(2):701-10.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.201600832R>
21. Simon MC, Strassburger K, Nowotny B, Kolb H, Nowotny P, Burkart V, et al. Intake of lactobacillus reuteri improves incretin and insulin secretion in glucose-tolerant humans: a proof of concept. *Diabetes Care.* 2015;38(10):1827-34. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc14-2690>
22. Pathak P, Xie C, Nichols RG, Ferrell JM, Boehme S, Krausz KW, et al. Intestine farnesoid X receptor agonist and the gut microbiota activate G-protein bile acid receptor-1 signaling to improve metabolism. *Hepatology.* 2018;68:1574-88. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.29857>
23. Jiang C, Xie C, Lv Y, Li J, Krausz KW, Shi J, et al. Intestine-selective farnesoid X receptor inhibition improves obesity-related metabolic dysfunction. *Nat Commun.* 2015;6:10166.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10166>
24. Yang M, Fukui H, Eda H, Kitayama Y, Hara K, Kodani M, et al. Involvement of gut microbiota in the association between gastrointestinal motility and 5HT expression/M2 macrophage abundance in the gastrointestinal tract. *Mol Med Rep.* 2017;16:3482-8.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.3892/mmr.2017.6955>
25. Koh A, De Vadder F, Kovatcheva-Datchary P, Backhed F. From dietary fiber to host physiology: short-chain fatty acids as key bacterial metabolites. *Cell.* 2016;165:1332-45.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2016.05.041>
26. Koval S, Iushko K, Starchenko T. The relations of apelin with the carbohydrate metabolism in hypertensive patients with type 2 diabetes or without it. *Endocrine Abstracts 19th European Congress of Endocrinology Lisbon, Portugal; 2017 May 20-23;49:458.*
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1530/endoabs.49.EP458>
27. Koval S, Snigurska I, Grozna L, Bozhko V. Features changes blood levels adiponektin in patients with essential hypertension and obesity and impaired glucose tolerance. *Journal of Hypertension.* 2014;32(e-Suppl.1):362.
28. Sun KY, Xu D-H, Xie C, Plummer S, Tang J, Yang XF, Ji XH. Lactobacillus paracasei modulates LPS-induced inflammatory cytokine release by monocyte-macrophages via the up-regulation of negative regulators of NF-kappaB signaling in a TLR2-dependent manner. *Cytokine.* 2017;92:1-11.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cyto.2017.01.003>
29. Liu WC, Yang M-C, Wu Y-Y, Chen P-H, Hsu C-M, Chen L-W. Lactobacillus plantarum reverse diabetes-induced Fmo3 and ICAM expression in mice through enteric dysbiosis-related c-Jun NH2-terminal kinase pathways. *PloS ONE.* 2018;13(5):e0196511.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0196511>
30. Breyner NM, Michon C, de Sousa CS, Boas PBV, Chain F, Azevedo V A et al. Microbial anti-inflammatory molecule (MAM) from faecalibacterium prausnitzii shows a protective effect on DNBS and DSS-Induced colitis model in mice through inhibition of NF-kappaB pathway. *Front Microbiol.* 2017;8:114.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00114>
31. Suarez-Zamorano N, Fabbiano S, Chevalier C, Stojanovic O, Colin DJ, Stevanovic A, et al. Microbiota depletion promotes browning of white adipose tissue and reduces obesity. *Nat Med.* 2015;21:1497-501.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.3994>
32. Pichette J, Fynn-Sackey N, Gagnon J. Hydrogen sulfide and sulfate prebiotic stimulates the secretion of GLP-1 and improves glycemia in male mice. *Endocrinology.* 2017;158:3416-25.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2017-00391>
33. He Y, Wu W, Zheng HM, Li P, McDonald D, Sheng H-F, et al. Regional variation limits applications of healthy gut microbiome reference ranges and disease models. *Nat Med.* 2018;24(10):1532-5.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0164-x>
34. Koval SM, Yushko KO, Snihurska IO, Starchenko TG, Pankiv IV, Lytvynova OM, Mysnychenko OV. Relations of angiotensin-(1-7) with hemodynamic and cardiac structural and functional parameters in patients with hypertension and type 2 diabetes. *Arterial Hypertens.* 2019;23(3):183-9.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.5603/AH.a2019.0012>
35. Bala V, Rajagopal S, Kumar DP, Nalli AD, Mahavadi S, Sanyal AJ, et al. Release of GLP-1 and PYY in response to the activation of G protein-coupled bile acid receptor TGR5 is mediated by Epac/PLC-epsilon pathway and modulated by endogenous H2S. *Front Physiol.* 2014;5:420.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2014.00420>

36. Gurung M, Li Z, You H, Rodrigues R, Jump DB, Morgun A, Shulzhenko N. Role of gut microbiota in type 2 diabetes pathophysiology. *EBioMedicine*. 2020;51:102590. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2019.11.051>
37. Zhu C, Song K, Shen Z, Quan Y, Tan B, Luo W, Wu S, Tang K, Yang Z, Wang X. Roseburia intestinalis inhibits interleukin-17 excretion and promotes regulatory T cells differentiation in colitis. *Molecular medicine reports*. 2018;17(6):7567-74. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3892/mmr.2018.8833>
38. Priyadarshini M, Wicksteed B, Schiltz GE, Gilchrist A, Layden BT. SCFA receptors in pancreatic beta cells: novel diabetes targets? *Trends Endocrinol Metab*. 2016;27:653-64. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tem.2016.03.011>
39. Shapiro H, Kolodziejczyk AA, Halstuch D, Elinav E. Bile acids in glucose metabolism in health and disease. *J Exp Med*. 2018;215:383-96. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.20171965>
40. Xu YH, Gao CL, Guo HL, Zhang WQ, Huang W, Tang SS, Gan WJ, Xu Y, Zhou H, Zhu Q. Sodium butyrate supplementation ameliorates diabetic inflammation in db/db mice. *J Endocrinol*. 2018;238(3):231-44. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1530/JOE-18-0137>
41. Stange EF. Gut microbiome, metabolic syndrome, and atherosclerosis. In: *The ESC Textbook of Cardiovascular Medicine*. Third edition. Edited by: A. John Camm, Thomas F. Luscher, Gerald Mauer, Patrick W. Serruys. OXFORD University press. 2019;1082-5.
42. Tong X, Xu J, Lian F, Yu X, Zhao Y, Xu L, et al. Structural alteration of gut microbiota during the amelioration of human type 2 diabetes with hyperlipidemia by metformin and a traditional Chinese herbal formula: a multicenter, randomized, open label clinical trial. *MBio*. 2018;9(3):e02392-17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.02392-17>
43. Kim M, Furuzono T, Yamakuni K, Li Y, Kim YI, Takahashi H, et al. 10-oxo-12(Z)-octadecenoic acid, a linoleic acid metabolite produced by gut lactic acid bacteria, enhances energy metabolism by activation of TRPV1. *FASEB J*. 2017;31:5036-48. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.201700151R>
44. Psichas A, Sleeth ML, Murphy KG, Brooks L, Bewick GA, Hanyaloglu AC, et al. The short chain fatty acid propionate stimulates GLP-1 and PYY secretion via free fatty acid receptor 2 in rodents. *Int J Obes*. 2015;39:424-9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ijo.2014.153>
45. Torres S, Fabersani E, Marquez A, Gauffin-Cano P. Adipose tissue inflammation and metabolic syndrome. The proactive role of probiotics. *Eur J Nutr*. 2019;58(1):27-43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00394-018-1790-2>
46. Cosentino F, Grant PJ, Aboyans V, Bailey CJ, Ceriello A, Delgado V, et al. 2019 ESC Guidelines on diabetes, pre-diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases developed in collaboration with the EASD: The Task Force for diabetes, pre-diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes (EASD). *European Heart Journal*. 2020;41(2):255-323. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehz486>

СПИСОК ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

1. Белоусова О. Н., Сиротина С. С., Якунченко Т. И., Жернакова Н. И. Молекулярные и генетические механизмы патогенеза сахарного диабета 2 типа. *Научные ведомости БелГУ. Сер. Медицина. Фармация*. 2015. Т. 213, № 16. Вып. 31. С. 12-19. URL: <http://dspace.bsu.edu.ru/handle/123456789/23761>
2. Коваль С. М., Юшко К. О., Снігурська І. О. Кишкова мікробіота і артеріальна гіпертензія: огляд літератури. *Запорозький медичинський журнал*. 2020. Т. 22, № 4. С. 561-567. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14739/2310-1210.2020.4.208409>
3. Лизогуб В. Г., Крамарьова В. Н., Мельничук І. О. Роль змін мікробіоти кишківника в патогенезі серцево-судинних захворювань: огляд літератури. *Запорозький медичинський журнал*. 2019. Т. 21, № 5 (116). С. 672-678. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14739/2310-1210.2019.5.179462>
4. Сахарный диабет типа 2: от теории к практике / под ред. академика РАН И. И. Дедова, чл.-кор. РАН М. В. Шестаковой. Москва: ООО "Изд-во "Медицинское информационное агенство". 2016. 576 с.
5. Фадеенко Г. Д., Гриднев А. Е. Синдром раздраженного кишечника и кишечный микробиом. От патогенетических механизмов к лечению. *Гастроэнтерология*. 2018. Т. 52, № 4. С. 24-29.
6. Aberrant intestinal microbiota in individuals with prediabetes / K. H. Allin et al. *Diabetologia*. 2018. Vol. 61. P. 810-820. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-018-4550-1>
7. Akkermansia muciniphila can reduce the damage of gluco/lipototoxicity, oxidative stress and inflammation, and normalize intestine microbiota in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats / L. Zhang et al. *Pathog and Dis*. 2018. Vol. 76, No. 4. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/femspd/fty028>
8. Antidiabetic (type 2) effects of lactobacillus G15 and Q14 in rats through regulation of intestinal permeability and microbiota / P. Tian et al. *Food Funct*. 2016. Vol. 7. P. 3789-3797. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6fo00831c>
9. A specific gut microbiota dysbiosis of type 2 diabetic mice induces GLP-1 resistance through an enteric NO-dependent and gut-brain axis mechanism / E. Grasset et al. *Cell Metab*. 2017. Vol. 26. P. 278. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2017.06.003>
10. Aw W., Fukuda S. Understanding the role of the gut ecosystem in diabetes mellitus. *J Diabetes Investig*. 2018. Vol. 9. P. 5-12. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jdi.12673>

11. Aydin W., Nieuwdorp M., Gerdes V. The gut microbiome as a target for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. *Curr Diab Rep.* 2018. Vol. 18, No. 8. P. 55. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-018-1020-6>
12. Bleau C., Karelis A. D., St-Pierre D. H., Lamontagne L. Crosstalk between intestinal microbiota, adipose tissue and skeletal muscle as an early event in systemic low-grade inflammation and the development of obesity and diabetes. *Diabetes Metab Res Rev.* 2015. Vol. 31. P. 545-561. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/dmrr.2617>
13. Differential changes in gut microbiota after gastric bypass and sleeve gastrectomy bariatric surgery vary according to diabetes remission / R. Murphy et al. *Obes Surg.* 2017. Vol. 27. P. 917-925. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11695-016-2399-2>
14. GLP-1 response to oral glucose is reduced in prediabetes, screen-detected type 2 diabetes, and obesity and influenced by sex: the ADDITION-PRO study / K. Faerch et al. *Diabetes.* 2015. Vol. 64. P. 2513-2525. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2337/db14-1751>
15. GPR43 potentiates beta-cell function in obesity / J. C. McNelis et al. *Diabetes.* 2015. Vol. 64. P. 3203-3217. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2337/db14-1938>
16. Grard C., Vidal H. Impact of Gut Microbiota on Host Glycemic Control. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).* 2019. Vol. 30. P. 0-29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2019.00029>
17. Gut bacteria selectively promoted by dietary fibers alleviate type 2 diabetes / L. Zhao et al. *Science.* 2018. Vol. 359. P. 1151-1156. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao5774>
18. Harsch I. A., Konturek P. C. The role of gut microbiota in obesity and type 2 and type 1 diabetes mellitus: new insights into "Old" diseases. *Med Sci.* 2018. Vol. 6. E32. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/medsci6020032>
19. Hulston C. J., Churnside A. A., Venables M. C. Probiotic supplementation prevents high-fat, overfeeding-induced insulin resistance in human subjects. *Br J Nutr.* 2015. Vol. 113, No. 4. P. 596-602. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114514004097>
20. IL-10 prevents aging-associated inflammation and insulin resistance in skeletal muscle / S. Dagdeviren et al. *FASEB J.* 2017. Vol. 31. P. 701-710. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.201600832R>
21. Intake of lactobacillus reuteri improves incretin and insulin secretion in glucose-tolerant humans: a proof of concept / M. C. Simon et al. *Diabetes Care.* 2015. Vol. 38, No. 10. P. 1827-1834. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc14-2690>
22. Intestine farnesoid X receptor agonist and the gut microbiota activate G-protein bile acid receptor-1 signaling to improve metabolism / P. Pathak et al. *Hepatology.* 2018. Vol. 68. P. 1574-1588. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.29857>
23. Intestine-selective farnesoid X receptor inhibition improves obesity-related metabolic dysfunction / C. Jiang et al. *Nat Commun.* 2015. Vol. 6. P. 10166. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10166>
24. Involvement of gut microbiota in the association between gastrointestinal motility and 5HT expression/M2 macrophage abundance in the gastrointestinal tract / M. Yang et al. *Mol Med Rep.* 2017. Vol. 16. P. 3482-3488. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3892/mmr.2017.6955>
25. Koh A., De Vadder F., Kovatcheva-Datchary P., Bäckhed F. From dietary fiber to host physiology: short-chain fatty acids as key bacterial metabolites. *Cell.* 2016. Vol. 165. P. 1332-1345. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2016.05.041>
26. Koval S., Iushko K., Starchenko T. The relations of apelin with the carbohydrate metabolism in hypertensive patients with type 2 diabetes or without it. *Endocrine Abstracts.* 2017. 19th European Congress of endocrinology Lisbon, Portugal. 2017. 20-23 May. (Vol. 49). EP458. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1530/endoabs.49.EP458>
27. Koval S., Snigurska I., Grozna L., Bozhko V. Features changes blood levels adiponektin in patients with essential hypertension and obesity and impaired glucose tolerance. *Journal of Hypertension.* 2014. Vol. 32. e-Suppl. 1. P. 362.
28. Lactobacillus paracasei modulates LPS-induced inflammatory cytokine release by monocyte-macrophages via the up-regulation of negative regulators of NF-kappaB signaling in a TLR2-dependent manner / K. Y. Sun et al. *Cytokine.* 2017. Vol. 92. P. 1-11. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cyto.2017.01.003>
29. Lactobacillus plantarum reverse diabetes-induced Fmo3 and ICAM expression in mice through enteric dysbiosis-related c-Jun NH2-terminal kinase pathways / W. C. Liu et al. *PLoS ONE.* 2018. Vol. 13, No. 5. e0196511. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0196511>
30. Microbial anti-inflammatory molecule (MAM) from faecalibacterium prausnitzii shows a protective effect on DNBS and DSS-Induced colitis model in mice through inhibition of NF-kappaB pathway / N. M. Breyner et al. *Front Microbiol.* 2017. Vol. 8. P. 114. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00114>
31. Microbiota depletion promotes browning of white adipose tissue and reduces obesity / N. Suárez-Zamorano et al. *Nat Med.* 2015. Vol. 21. P. 1497-1501. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.3994>
32. Pichette J., Fynn-Sackey N., Gagnon J. Hydrogen sulfide and sulfate prebiotic stimulates the secretion of GLP-1 and improves glycemia in male mice. *Endocrinology.* 2017. Vol. 158. P. 3416-3425. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2017-00391>
33. Regional variation limits applications of healthy gut microbiome reference ranges and disease models / Y. He et al. *Nat Med.* 2018. Vol. 24, No. 10. P. 1532-1535. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0164-x>
34. Relations of angiotensin-(1-7) with hemodynamic and cardiac structural and functional parameters in patients with hypertension and type 2 diabetes / S. M. Koval et al. *Arterial Hypertens.* 2019. Vol. 23, No. 3. P. 183-189. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5603/AH.a2019.0012>
35. Release of GLP-1 and PYY in response to the activation of G protein-coupled bile acid receptor TGR5 is mediated by Epac/PLC-epsilon pathway and modulated by endogenous H2S / V. Bala et al. *Front Physiol.* 2014. Vol. 5. P. 420. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2014.00420>

36. Role of gut microbiota in type 2 diabetes pathophysiology / M. Gurung et al. *EBioMedicine*. 2020. Vol. 51. P. 102590. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2019.11.051>
37. Roseburia intestinalis inhibits interleukin-17 excretion and promotes regulatory T cells differentiation in colitis / C. Zhu et al. *Molecular medicine reports*. 2018. Vol. 17, No. 6. P. 7567-7574. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3892/mmr.2018.8833>
38. SCFA receptors in pancreatic beta cells: novel diabetes targets? / M. Priyadarshini et al. *Trends Endocrinol Metab*. 2016. Vol. 27. P. 653-664. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tem.2016.03.011>
39. Shapiro H., Kolodziejczyk A. A., Halstuch D., Elinav E. Bile acids in glucose metabolism in health and disease. *J Exp Med*. 2018. Vol. 215. P. 383-396. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.20171965>
40. Sodium butyrate supplementation ameliorates diabetic inflammation in db/db mice / Y. H. Xu et al. *J Endocrinol*. 2018. Vol. 238, No. 3. P. 231-244. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1530/JOE-18-0137>
41. Stange E. F. Gut microbiome, metabolic syndrome, and atherosclerosis. In: *The ESC Textbook of Cardiovascular Medicine*. 3rd ed. / Ed. A. J. Camm, T. F. Luscher, G. Mauer, P. W. Serruys. OXFORD University press, 2019. P. 1082-1085.
42. Structural alteration of gut microbiota during the amelioration of human type 2 diabetes with hyperlipidemia by metformin and a traditional Chinese herbal formula: a multicenter, randomized, open label clinical trial / X. Tong et al. *MBio*. 2018. Vol. 9, No. 3. pii:e02392-17. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.02392-17>
43. 10-oxo-12(Z)-octadecenoic acid, a linoleic acid metabolite produced by gut lactic acid bacteria, enhances energy metabolism by activation of TRPV1 / M. Kim et al. *FASEB J*. 2017. Vol. 31. P. 5036-5048. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.201700151R>
44. The short chain fatty acid propionate stimulates GLP-1 and PYY secretion via free fatty acid receptor 2 in rodents / A. Psichas et al. *Int J Obes*. 2015. Vol. 39. P. 424-429. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ijo.2014.153>
45. Torres S., Fabersani E., Marquez A., Gauffin-Cano P. Adipose tissue inflammation and metabolic syndrome. The proactive role of probiotics. *Eur J Nutr*. 2019. Vol. 58, No. 1. P. 27-43. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00394-018-1790-2>
46. 2019 ESC Guidelines on diabetes, pre-diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases developed in collaboration with the EASD: The Task Force for diabetes, pre-diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes (EASD) / F. Cosentino et al. *European Heart Journal*. 2020. Vol. 41, No. 2. P. 255-323. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehz486>

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